

Financial Development and Tertiary School Enrollment Nexus in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper empirically investigates the financial development function for tertiary school enrollment in Nigeria by using yearly time series data during the period 1981–2022. Research variables are tertiary school enrollment (TSER), financial deepening (FD), credit to the private sector (CPS), gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC), remittances from abroad (RMT), and capital expenditure on social services (SSCEXP). The long-run and short-run elasticities of variables were examined using the bounds testing cointegration method. The results of the analysis show that financial deepening has no long-term relationship with tertiary school enrollment. GDP per capita negatively impacts tertiary school enrollment, indicating income inequality. However, credit to the private sector positively influences tertiary school enrollment, with an increase in LCPS leading to a 77% increase in enrollment. Remittances from abroad have a negative relationship, while capital expenditure on social services (LSSCEXP) positively impacts tertiary school enrollment, with an increase in LSSCEXP leading to a 78% increase in enrollment. According to the error correction model, there is a long-run relationship among variables, indicating that fluctuations in financial development are adjusted at a speed of approximately 101.4% to ensure long-run convergence to equilibrium. The study suggests that in order for prospective students to benefit from credit, Nigeria's financial systems must first become more accessible. This is because low participation in tertiary education might result in a skills gap that hinders productivity and economic growth.

Keywords: Tertiary Education; Financial Deepening; GDP per capita; Remittances; ARDL

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping a nation's future, and efforts to improve tertiary enrollment rates are vital for sustainable development. Tertiary education, provided by universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education, is a critical stage that follows secondary education and precedes entry into the workforce or further studies at the postgraduate level (Erhieyovwe and Governor, 2019).

Many studies on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria, particularly in the last 20 years, have paid little to no attention to the examination of government policy rationale. The number of students attending tertiary educational institutions had been increasing before the first private university in Nigeria was founded in 1999. It is disheartening to observe that, in spite of the growth of private universities, the chances of getting admitted to respectable universities are decreasing on a daily basis (Ademola, Ogundipe, and Babatunde, 2014). Prospective students who are eager to enroll in tertiary institutions face numerous obstacles. The factors include a scarcity of high-quality tertiary institutions, inadequate teaching facilities, a shortage of spaces to accommodate the growing number of prospective students, and, most importantly, a lack of funding.

A higher GDP per capita can lead to increased household incomes, making education more affordable. However, income inequality may persist, affecting certain segments of the population. Increased credit to the private sector can stimulate economic activities, including education investment. Remittances from abroad can improve households' capacity to invest in education, but dependence on remittances may not be sustainable. Capital expenditure in the education sector can lead to new facilities, improved infrastructure, and enhanced educational quality, but insufficient or mismanaged funds could limit the positive impact on tertiary school enrollment.

The number of students attending tertiary schools in Nigeria has increased significantly over time. There is a growing need for tertiary education due to factors like growth in the population, increased educational aspirations, and the realisation of the value of advanced degrees in the workforce. Even with the increase in enrollment, access-related issues continue to exist. According to the World Bank (2023), Nigeria's gross enrolment rate for tertiary education was 11.8% in 2018. Out of the eligible population, this percentage indicates the fraction of students enrolled in tertiary institutions. Over time, there has been a noticeable increase in the percentage. Notably, according to Figure 1, the highest growth rate was recorded in 2003 at 103.1%, while the lowest was recorded in 2000 at -26.1%. The main source of this is financial development, which has reduced financial obstacles to tertiary education and altered students' ability to pay for their schooling.

Financial development, which enables families to set aside money for their children's tertiary education, can have a significant impact on planning for education. Additionally, it may be in line with government initiatives like educational funding and subsidies that promote tertiary education. Families can invest in tertiary education by raising family income levels through the development of the financial sector. Small loans or other financial support can be obtained through community banking and microfinance (Mamadou and Ongo-Nkoa, 2022). Collaborations between the public and commercial sectors can increase funding for tertiary education. Financial development may strengthen the foundation of education and provide families and students with the information they need to make wise financial decisions for their education. Enhancing the perceived value of tertiary education can also result from aligning it with the labour market. Financial development can also facilitate social and economic mobility. The focus should be on efficient loans to help impoverished students pursue postsecondary education rather than just providing more aid in the form of school loans. Still, a significant portion of students who would like to enroll in postsecondary education are unable to do so due to financial constraints.

To our knowledge, documentary evidence of the impact of financial development on tertiary school enrollment specifically is still nonexistent. Except for Thierry and Emmanuel (2023), who concentrated on the three levels of education (primary, secondary, and tertiary) in the 37 countries in sub-Saharan Africa over the period 2000–2018, other studies have examined the various facets of financial development, including foreign direct investments (Kaulihowa & Adjasi, 2019), external aid (Yogo, 2017), and the calibre of institutions (Ouedraogo et al., 2021). Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to examine the impact of financial development on tertiary enrollment in Nigeria. This article contributes greatly to the literature and fills this work gap. Much more, it allows over a recent period to appreciate the role of financial development on tertiary enrollment in Nigeria. The paper is organised as follows: After this introduction, Section 2 presents the theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 presents the methodology.

The results are given and discussed in Section 4. The paper concludes in Section 5.

Figure: % Change in Tertiary School Enrollment Ratio

Source: Researcher's calculation from World Bank data, 2023

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, because the financial sector offers superior financial intermediation services, its growth is critical to sustained economic growth (Becker and Knudsen, 2002). A well-developed domestic financial sector is positively correlated with higher growth and education, according to an increasing body of empirical research (Arora & Ratnasiri, 2011; Beck et al., 2000; Ibrahim & Alagidede, 2018; Bencivenga & Smith, 1991; Levine et al., 2000).

Differing perspectives on who benefits from the outcomes of financial inclusion exist. Some studies (Bhandari, 2018) claim that the poor are the main beneficiaries of financial inclusion; others (Ghosh and Vinod, 2017; Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2013; Swamy, 2014) contend that women gain from financial inclusion; still others think that financial inclusion is good for the financial system and the economy (Mehrotra and Yetman, 2015; Swamy, 2014; Ozili, 2018). Women and the poor are not the only groups that stand to gain from financial inclusion; youth, the elderly, institutionalised people, people with disabilities, and those expelled from the financial industry due to criminal activity are among the others who have not received enough attention in the literature. Four ideas, according to Ozili (2020), explain who gains from financial inclusion.

The public good theory of financial inclusion suggests that formal financial services should be treated as a public good, providing unrestricted access to finance for everyone. This theory suggests that everyone benefits from financial inclusion, regardless of their status, income level, or demographic differences. The government can subsidize the cost of providing these services, and the government can take responsibility for promoting financial inclusion. However, the theory has three drawbacks: it does not address the real cause of financial exclusion, may require government subsidies, and assumes that the provision of formal financial services is free or low-cost. Additionally, the theory assumes that the cost of these services is underpriced, which may not be sustainable in the long term, even with public funding.

The dissatisfaction theory of financial inclusion suggests that financial inclusion programs should first target individuals who left the formal financial sector due to dissatisfaction with the rules or unpleasant experiences. This theory suggests that resolving dissatisfaction in the formal financial sector is easier than extending programs to other members of the population. Banked adults may become dissatisfied due to financial fraud, theft, long waiting times, high transaction costs, and excessive bank charges. The theory has merits, such as reducing voluntary financial exclusion and identifying financially excluded individuals. However, it does not prioritize financial inclusion for everyone and assumes that financial exclusion is caused by customers' dissatisfaction with the rules of engagement. Additionally, individuals may voluntarily exit the formal financial sector for religious and personal reasons.

The vulnerable group theory of financial inclusion suggests that financial inclusion programs should be aimed at vulnerable members of society who are most affected by economic hardships, such as poor, young, women, and elderly people. This can be achieved through government-to-person social cash transfers into their accounts, encouraging others to join the formal financial sector. This approach can make vulnerable individuals feel compensated for existing income inequality and provide them with opportunities to catch up with other segments of society. However, the theory has some drawbacks, such as not prioritizing financial inclusion for everyone, ignoring non-vulnerable individuals outside the formal financial sector, and assuming women are a vulnerable group, which could lead to societal resentment and increase social inequality. Ultimately, the theory should be targeted to reduce financial exclusion and improve financial inclusion for all.

The systems theory of financial inclusion posits that financial inclusion outcomes are influenced by existing sub-systems, such as economic, social, and financial systems. Changes in these sub-systems can significantly impact the expected financial inclusion outcome. The theory suggests that the efficiency and effectiveness of these sub-systems determine the success or failure of a national financial inclusion agenda. The theory acknowledges the role of existing economic, financial, and social structures in promoting financial inclusion, provides a macro-perspective, and considers the interrelationship among sub-systems. However, it has some drawbacks, such as not recognizing the influence of external factors on financial inclusion outcomes, and assuming a direct relationship between financial inclusion outcomes and the systems they rely on.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

To the best of our knowledge, there is no existing literature on the impact of financial development on tertiary school enrollment. Although a few empirical studies focus on whether financial development increases education levels, Thierry and Emmanuel (2023) found that financial development increases school enrollment and improves primary and secondary education for both genders, except for males at the tertiary level. The study suggests improving the financial market and institutions in SSA.

Banerjee and Newman (1993) and Galor and Zeira (1993) have found a negative linear association between financial development and education. Their core thesis is that because households lack assets, credit histories, and social networks, financial market defects such as financial asymmetries, transaction costs, and contract enforcement costs can disproportionately harm them. Thus, even with high-yield projects, credit might be restricted to the poor. Consequently,

there is inefficient capital allocation and less social mobility for the poor (Levine & Zervos, 1998).

Enrollment in African educational systems, ranging from primary to higher education, including vocational education, has experienced a record-breaking spike in enrollment. These are stylized facts. According to data from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2018), there were 286.7 million learners in 2017, as opposed to 142.6 million in 1998. Due to strong social demand, this increase has prompted modifications to institutional structure, governance, teacher preparation programmes, and instructional methodologies in general. A greater emphasis on education systems in Africa is a result of various regional and global challenges, including the goals of the Agenda 2063 strategy for Africa, the continental education strategy 2016–2025, and the expansion of the number of goals and education indicators under the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). 4.

Africa exhibits a wide range of sub-regional situations, yet in 2019, the continent still had low rates of school exclusion. The rate of exclusion in Sub-Saharan Africa is 21%, which is higher than that of North Africa (11%). Furthermore, among sub-Saharan Africa's states, West African ones often demonstrate the most worrisome performance. The sub-region is home to a large number of young, illiterate people (15–24 years old). Despite a significant drop, the proportion of unschooled children in West Africa remains a critical concern. More than 25% of children are prohibited from attending primary school. Nearly 20% of all children globally did not attend school in 2010. Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa. The main reason for this situation is a lack of financial resources. In a similar vein, the financial industry has expanded rapidly in most Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries since the early 1990s. They are still more constrained than the rest of the globe, though. In addition, banks remain the primary financial institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa, mostly providing loans to large corporations. Thierry and Emmanuel (2023) note that despite the rapid growth of non-bank financial intermediaries, particularly in the insurance and microfinance sectors, the sizes of these sectors relative to the GDP and population have not increased. Gross tertiary enrolment and GDP per capita are significantly correlated, according to a UNESCO IESALC (2020) assessment. According to the paper, an increase in GDP per capita is typically associated with an increase in university enrollment.

Statistics indicate that banks' contribution to financial intermediation in Sub-Saharan Africa is still very minimal when compared to other nations, even with a catch-up during the 1990s. The average bank deposit/GDP ratio in 2020 was almost 43% in middle-income countries (MICs) in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), 30% in low-income countries (LICs) inside SSA, and 34% in low-income countries (LICs) outside of SSA (BEI, 2020). It should be noted that, depending on the relative income levels of the different countries, the depth varies considerably. The financial sectors of PRI ASSs are usually much deeper and more diverse than those of LICs, which have smaller financial sectors and more restricted institutional coverage. The expansion of the financial industry and the increasing importance of bank deposits are associated with a decline in the ratio of strictly defined money to broadly defined money. For example, in 2019, the broad money M2/GDP ratios for PRI and PFRASS were 47% and 32%, respectively. The fact that the M1/M2 ratio has barely altered since 2000 illustrates how difficult it is to achieve financial depth. According to Thierry and Emmanuel (2023), financial markets in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) have a larger M1/M2 ratio than those in other areas. This suggests that these countries still have a long way to go before moving away from cash-based payment systems.

Research indicates a clear connection between remittance flows and educational investments. Remittances incentivize parents to send their kids to school, boost primary school enrollment, and lessen child labour. They also offer chances for higher learning. Numerous studies have shown that there is a strong correlation between overseas remittances and educational advancement. Adams and Cuecuecha (2010); Di Maria and Lazarova (2012); Vogel and Korinek (2012); Zhunio, Vishwasrao, and Chiang (2012); Acosta, Fajnzylber, & Lopez (2007).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Sources

The data employed in this study are yearly time series data of tertiary school enrollment (% gross) (TSER), Financial Deepening (FD), credit to the private sector (CPS), Gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC), Remittances from abroad (RMT), and Capital expenditure on social services (SSCEXP). The World Bank's and the Nigerian Central Bank's statistical databases are the sources of all data. All the variables, aside from tertiary school enrollment, interest rates and inflation rates are displayed as natural logarithms.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables and Data Sources

S/ No	Variables	Measurement	Expected sign	Sources of Data
	Tertiary school enrolment ratio (TSER)	The tertiary enrollment ratio is the proportion of total enrollment, regardless of age, to the population of the age group that corresponds to the level of education shown.	-	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.TER.ENRR.FE
	Financial deepening (FD), a proxy for financial development	Refers to the process through which an economy's financial systems grow and develop over time.	Positive	Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin volume 33, December 2022. A.24.2
	Credit to the private sector (CPS) a proxy for financial depth	Refers to the total amount of financing that financial institutions, such as banks, provide to private businesses and individuals within a specific economy.	Positive	Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin volume 33, December 2022. A.24.2
	Gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC)	It analyzes Nigeria's GDP per capita and gauges the prosperity of Nigerians by looking at our GDP growth. It is computed by dividing the nation's GDP by its total population. We expect a positive relationship between the variables.	Positive	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.KN?locations=NG
	Remittances from abroad (RMT)	Refers to the funds or financial transfers that people send from another country, typically the one in which they are employed or live, to their own country. It represents a sizable source of income, and they can have a big effect on the local economy.	Positive	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.TRF.PWKR.CD.DT
	Capital expenditure on social services (SSCEXP)	It is used to capture the fiscal policy instruments. It measures the payments for the acquisition of fixed capital assets, stock, land, or intangible assets in the social and community services sectors, which include education, health, and other service sectors.	Positive	Central bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin volume 33, December 2022. B.1.3

Source: Authors Compilation, 2023

3.2 Method of Data Analysis

We applied the ARDL model initially proposed by Pesaran and Shin, (1999) then extended by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith, (2001). There are several reasons for choosing this estimator. First, is that estimating the above equation with ordinary least squares (OLS) could lead to inefficient estimates, as OLS does not control for fixed effects and may suffer from variable omission bias. Second, it is useful for testing combinations of level variables with varying orders of integration, such as I(0) or I(1). In addition, it is inapplicable to regressors with an I(2) order of integration. Third, the serial correlation and endogenous regressor issues could be simultaneously resolved by reversing the order. The Granger causality test analyzed if a one-time series Granger causes the other or whether a time series can be used to predict the others. The general model used to estimate the output determinants is as follows:

3.3 Modelspecification

The recent work of Thierry and Emmanuel (2023), which highlighted whether financial development raises education levels, served as inspiration for the model. The modified version of the model is specified as follows:

$$TSER = f(FD, CPS, GDPPC, RMT, SSCEXP) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1)'s ARDL framework can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LTSER_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 LTSER_{t-1} + \beta_2 LFD_{2t-1} + \beta_3 LCPS_{3t-1} + \beta_4 LGDPPC_{4t-1} + \beta_5 LRMT_{5t-1} + \beta_6 LSSCEXP_{6t-1} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^p \delta_j \Delta LTSER_{t-j} + \sum_{l=0}^q \varphi_l \Delta LFD_{2t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^q \delta_m \Delta LCPS_{3t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^q \eta_n \Delta LGDPPC_{4t-n} + \sum_{n=0}^q \eta_n \Delta LRMT_{5t-n} + \sum_{a=0}^q \mu_a \Delta LSSCEXP_{6t-a} \\ & + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The model uses the ordinary least squares (OLS) method to estimate the lagged levels of variables and test their joint significance using the F-test. The Wald test is used to examine the long-run relationship between variables. The test results are analyzed using the F-statistic, which is non-standard under the null hypothesis. If the F-statistics exceed the upper level bound, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating cointegration over the long term. The short and long-run dynamic relationships can be estimated after implementing the ARDL method. As a result, Equation (2) can be rewritten as follows by adding the error correction term:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=0}^p \delta_j \Delta LTSER_{t-j} + \sum_{l=0}^q \varphi_l \Delta LFD_{2t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^q \delta_m \Delta LCPS_{3t-m} + \sum_{n=0}^q \eta_n \Delta LGDPPC_{4t-n} + \sum_{n=0}^q \eta_n \Delta LRMT_{5t-n} + \sum_{a=0}^q \mu_a \Delta LSSCEXP_{6t-a} \\ \lambda(ECM)_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t-1} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The Error Correction Model (ECM) is a statistical analysis tool that measures the short- and long-term relationships between variables. It uses an error correction term (ECT) to measure how quickly long-run equilibrium deviations are adjusted. To demonstrate long-term equilibrium, the ECT_{t-1} term must be statistically significant and negative, indicating a force driving the variables towards equilibrium (Sargan, 1964).

4 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1 Preliminary Analysis

Table 2 shows that while LTSER, LFD, LCPS, and LRMT are stationary after first differencing, capital expenditure on social services (LSSCEXP) is stationary at levels when intercept and trend are taken into account. This demonstrates that the only variables present are I(0) and I(1). Therefore, it is appropriate to use the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method.

Table 2: Unit Root Tests Result

Variables	ADF Test Statistic				PP Test Statistic			
	Constant	Constant & Trend	None	First Difference	Constant	Constant & Trend	None	First Difference
<i>LTSER</i>	-1.44	-2.67	1.16	-7.48*	-1.56	-2.76	2.09	-12.40*
<i>LFD</i>	-0.96	-2.34	0.91	-5.93*	-0.83	-2.49	1.51	-6.33*
<i>LCPS</i>	0.95	-0.71	2.39	-4.59*	-0.88	-0.71	4.09	-4.53*
<i>LGPPC</i>	-1.09	-1.55	1.77	-4.24*	-0.47	-3.12	0.66	-4.24*
<i>LRMT</i>	-0.94	-1.62	1.43	-6.53*	-0.94	-1.83	1.43	-6.53*
<i>LSSCEXP</i>	-3.61*	-3.93	0.02	-10.61*	-3.86*	-4.01*	-0.37	-10.86*

Source: Authors’ construct using Eviews 9 (2023).

Notes (ADF): Test critical values at 5% (At level: constant = -2.94, Constant and trend = -3.53, none = -2.63 while at First difference = -2.95); P-value= Probability value, * signifies stationarity.

Notes (PP): Test critical values at 5% (At level: constant = -2.94, Constant and trend = -3.53, none = -2.63 while at First difference = -2.94); P-value= Probability value, * signifies stationarity.

The advantage of the PP test over the ADF test is that it corrects for heteroscedasticity and serial correlation in the error terms. The autoregressive process is estimated using a given number of lags in the non-parametric PP test, which does not pretest for serial correlation. Next, the test statistic is modified to take the errors’ serial correlation into consideration. In contrast, lag selection is an essential part of the testing process for other unit root tests, including the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test (Ihugba, 2023). Table 2 above shows the results of the ADF and PP tests.

4.2 Bounds Test for Cointegration

The bounds test for cointegration provides a solid foundation for assessing the likelihood of a long-term relationship. This is necessary in order to use the ARDL model.

Table 3: Results of Bounds Test for Cointegration

<i>Test Statistic</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>k</i>
<i>F-statistic</i>	3.837333	5
<i>Critical Value Bounds</i>		
<i>Significance</i>	<i>I0 Bound</i>	<i>I1 Bound</i>
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Authors’ construct using Eviews 9 (2023).

The F-statistics value (3.837333) in Table 3 is higher than the upper bounds’ values, or I(1). This means that the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no level of relationship and finds that there is long-run joint cointegration.

4.3 Long-Run Coefficients

When the bounds test for cointegration shows that there is a long-term relationship between tertiary school enrollment and the explanatory variables, the ARDL framework is used to get a better idea of the long-run coefficients.

Table 4: Long-Run Effect of Financial Development on Tertiary School

Selected Model: ARDL(3, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>Prob.*</i>
<i>TSER(-1)</i>	0.389620	0.181052	2.151975	0.0405**
<i>TSER(-2)</i>	-0.071474	0.200753	-0.356029	0.7246
<i>TSER(-3)</i>	-0.332598	0.174448	-1.906575	0.0673*
<i>LFD</i>	-0.685072	1.471648	-0.465514	0.6453
<i>LFD(-1)</i>	-1.739409	1.396181	-1.245833	0.2235
<i>LCPS</i>	0.770232	0.320815	2.400857	0.0235**
<i>LGDPCC</i>	-0.870529	4.760318	-0.182872	0.8563
<i>LGDPCC(-1)</i>	7.688248	5.009231	1.534816	0.1365
<i>LRMT</i>	-0.061859	0.193593	-0.319529	0.7518
<i>LSSCEXP</i>	0.786875	0.359285	2.190112	0.0373**
<i>LSSCEXP(-1)</i>	0.811002	0.363233	2.232730	0.0341**
<i>C</i>	-79.17040	33.86719	-2.337673	0.0271
<i>R-squared</i>	0.947672	<i>Mean dependent var</i>	7.178438	
<i>Adjusted R-squared</i>	0.926353	<i>S.D. dependent var</i>	3.205586	
<i>S.E. of regression</i>	0.869929	<i>Akaike info criterion</i>	2.806850	
<i>Sum squared resid</i>	20.43297	<i>Schwarz criterion</i>	3.318715	
<i>Log likelihood</i>	-42.73357	<i>Hannan-Quinn criter.</i>	2.990503	
<i>F-statistic</i>	44.45248	<i>Durbin-Watson stat</i>	1.982645	
<i>Prob(F-statistic)</i>	0.000000			

Note: 10%, 5%, and 1% levels are indicated by the symbols *, **, and ***, respectively.

Source: Authors' construct using Eviews 9 (2023).

Table 4 establishes that the variables that have a relationship with the growth of tertiary school enrollment in the long run are credit to the private sector (LCPS), and capital expenditure on social services (LSSCEXP). The coefficient of financial deepening in its first and second lags are negative and not significant at 1%, 5%, and 10%, hence there is no long-run relationship between tertiary school enrollment and financial deepening. This result is not expected; given that financial deepening which involves the expansion of financial services, will provide individuals and families with improved access to financing options. Which include student loans, scholarships, or other financial instruments that can support tertiary education. Similarly, GDP per capita in its first lag is found to relate negatively with the long-run growth of tertiary school enrollment. Hence, a unit increase in GDP per capita leads to a 87% decrease in tertiary school enrollment over the studied period although not significant, this result, has not attained the expected signs, and it is economically understood that when GDPPC increases income per person in a given country increases. It shows that Nigeria experiences significant income inequality, with a substantial portion of the population facing financial constraints. While the overall GDP per capita may be relatively high, the benefits may not be evenly distributed. Income inequality can limit access to tertiary education for a significant portion of the country's population. Meanwhile, the credit to the private sector (LCPS) in its second lag, is found in the

long run to also positively influence tertiary school enrolment. This implies that an increase in LCPS by one unit, leads to 77% increase in tertiary school enrolment. These positive results is highly expected since positive private sector credit indicates that investment and support from private entities in the education sector. The result also show that financial institutions are contributing to educational infrastructure or scholarship programs, encouraging tertiary school enrollment. Remittances from abroad which is expected to benefit tertiary school enrolment in the long run is not statistically significant and has a negative relationship.

Capital expenditure on social services (LSSCEXP) which a proxy for capital expenditure on education has a positive relationship with tertiary school enrollment. Thus a unit increase in the LSSCEXP increases the tertiary school enrollment in all the two lag years. This implies that an increase in LSSCEXP by one unit, leads to 78% increase in tertiary school enrolment

4.4 Short-run Dynamics

The ARDL has three components; the short-run, the long-run and the error-correction term (ECT). From Table 5, ECT is -1.014452 and it is significant at 1% with the expected negative sign. This gives another confirmation of the existence of a long-run relationship, indicating that fluctuations financial development (that is; above or below its equilibrium level) are adjusted at a speed of approximately 101.4%. To ensure long-run convergence to equilibrium

Table 5: Short Run Effects of Financial Development on Tertiary Enrollment

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
<i>C</i>	-78.042534	24.927481	-3.130783	0.0042
<i>D(TSER(-1))</i>	0.404072	0.201097	2.009338	0.0546*
<i>D(LFD(-1))</i>	-2.389942	1.377854	-1.734539	0.0942*
<i>D(LCPS(-))</i>	0.759259	0.303365	2.502790	0.0187**
<i>D(LGDPPC(-))</i>	6.720593	2.210717	3.040006	0.0052**
<i>D(LRMT(-))</i>	-0.060977	0.191860	-0.317823	0.7531
<i>D(LSSCEXP(-1))</i>	1.575114	0.489843	3.215547	0.0034***
<i>ECT(-1)</i>	-1.014452	0.225373	-4.501213	0.0001***

Note: 10%, 5%, and 1% levels are indicated by the symbols *, **, and ***, respectively.

Source: Authors' construct using Eviews 9 (2023).

The model again revealed that credit to the private sector (LCPS) positively affects tertiary school enrollment in the short-run. Similarly, the present coefficients of GDP per capita (GDPPC) and capital expenditure on social and community services (LSSCEXP) relates positively with the short-run growth of tertiary school enrollment, while the current financial development (LFD) and remittances from abroad (LRMT) relate negatively with tertiary school enrollment in the short run; though, only LFD presented a significant impact.

4.5 Diagnostic and Stability Test

The post-estimation result in Table VI indicates the model is free from serial correlation, heteroscedasticity, underfitting or overfitting, and it is normal.

Table 6: Outcome of Diagnostic and Stability Tests

S/No	Method	Lm Version	F-Stat Version
1	Serial correlation	$\chi^2(1) = 4.817799 (0.0899)$	$F(2,25) = 1.761808 (0.1924)$
2	Heteroscedasticity	$\chi^2(39) = 10.10713 (0.5208)$	$F(11,27) = 2.066365 (0.0610)$
3	Normality (Jarque-Bera)	$\chi^2 = 4.036869 (0.132863)$	Normal
4	Functional Form (RESET)	$\chi^2(26) = 0.857537 (0.3990)$	$F(1, 26) = 0.735370 (0.3990)$
5	CUSUM	Within 5% critical region	Stable
6	CUSUMSQ	Within 5% critical region	Stable

Source: Authors' construct using Eviews 9 (2023)

Table 7: Short Run Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LFD does not Granger Cause TSER	41	1.31308	0.2590
TSER does not Granger Cause LFD		3.16708	0.0831

Source: Authors' construct using Eviews 9 (2023)

The bounds test showed the existence of long-run relationship but it was silent on the direction of causality. Using the Pairwise Granger causality test, a significant F-statistic, the null hypothesis is accepted. Financial development does not granger-causes tertiary school enrollment, as in Table 7.

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The public good theory of financial inclusion, which encompasses financial development, contends that formal financial institutions ought to give everyone unfettered access to capital (Ozili, 2020). When the theory is applied to the education sector, it should result in higher tertiary enrollment rates, lower levels of economic inequality, higher levels of economic productivity, and government support. Services like affordable loans or microfinance should also provide individuals with the means to finance tertiary education, reducing disparities and promoting inclusive enrollment. Additionally, financial inclusion fosters entrepreneurship, which raises enrollment rates and promotes economic self-sufficiency. The long-term social advantages of education are emphasised by the public good theory, and financial inclusion advances these objectives by increasing access to education. At 1%, 5%, and 10%, the study did show that the financial development coefficient, or coefficient of financial deepening, was negative and not significant. This indicates that, at the time of the study, there was no sustained connection between attending postsecondary education and financial progress in Nigeria. The findings show that Nigeria's financial development is not addressing income inequality. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) "2019 Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria" study, over 83 million people, or 40% of the entire population, live below the national poverty line, which is set at 137,430 naira (\$381.75) per year (World Bank, 2020). The beneficial effect of financial development on tertiary school enrollment has been lessened as a result.

The results contradict the findings of Thierry and Emmanuel (2023), who found that financial development boosts enrolment in schools and enhances primary and secondary education for both sexes, with the exception of men at the tertiary level. The findings corroborate the findings

of Banerjee and Newman (1993), Galor and Zeira (1993), and Levine & Zervos (1998), who reported a negative linear association between financial development and education. Their core theory is that because households lack assets, credit histories, and social networks, financial market defects such as financial asymmetries, transaction costs, and contract enforcement costs can disproportionately harm them. Thus, even with high-yield projects, credit might be restricted to the poor. As a result, there is inefficient capital allocation and less social mobility for the poor. Likewise, there is a negative correlation observed between GDP per capita and the long-term increase in tertiary school enrollment. The findings imply that, between 1981 and 2022, there was an adverse relationship between the economic indicator (GDP per capita) and the educational outcome (enrollment in tertiary education). The number of students enrolled in tertiary education in Nigeria is influenced by a number of factors, including income disparity, high opportunity costs, and various educational systems. This finding is at variance with the UNESCO IESALC (2020) report, which proposed a substantial link between gross tertiary enrolment and GDP per capita.

Credit to the private sector (LCPS) is found in the long run to positively influence tertiary school enrolment. The result implies that increased access to credit for individuals and private businesses contributes to higher enrollment rates in tertiary education. It also shows that credit to the private sector in Nigeria has increased affordability, expansion of educational opportunities, diversification of fields of study, investment in skills and human capital, entrepreneurship and employment opportunities, economic growth and competitiveness, long-term development and innovation, social mobility, and a positive feedback loop. By providing financial means to pursue higher education, individuals can access tuition fees, textbooks, and other related expenses, enabling them to pursue higher education without significant financial barriers. The findings do not support the work of Levine & Zervos (1998).

Although remittances from abroad are predicted to increase tertiary school enrollment over time, their association with enrollment is negative and not statistically significant. This ultimately leads to long-term evidence that remittances might not be distributed equally throughout the population because they might not result in a widespread increase in the ability to afford tertiary education for all those who are expected to benefit from it if they primarily benefit certain households and not others. Enrollment in tertiary education is positively correlated with capital expenditure on social services (LSSCEXP), a proxy for capital expenditure on education. As a result, enrollment in tertiary education rises with a unit increase in the LSSCEXP.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper, we analyze the relationship between financial development and tertiary school enrollment in Nigeria over the period 1981–2022. Many students face challenges financing their tertiary education. Limited access to student loans and scholarships, coupled with economic constraints, can hinder enrollment rates. The lack of financial resources is presented as the main reason. The scarcity of work on this subject in Nigeria is the main motivation for writing this paper.

The regression analysis using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model shows that financial development does not increase tertiary school enrollment in Nigeria during the period of study. This paper, which contributes strongly to the literature on the subject, leads us to formulate four main implications.

First, in order for prospective students to benefit from credit, Nigeria's financial systems must first become more accessible. This is because low participation in tertiary education might result in a skills gap that hinders productivity and economic growth. It also exacerbates issues with economic diversification, lowers innovation and research, and increases unemployment and underemployment. Second, introduce and expand scholarship programs to provide financial support to deserving students. Scholarships can help reduce the financial burden on students and encourage enrollment, particularly among economically disadvantaged groups. Thirdly, in order to ensure better household income, GDP per capita must be improved. This will make it easier for parents and students to obtain bank financing, as limited access can impede people's capacity to improve their socioeconomic standing and may even exacerbate social inequality. Fourthly, because limited access to higher education can exacerbate income disparity and make it more difficult for people to get well-paying jobs, the state should, at the highest level, guarantee bank loans given to students, which they would repay with their first job.

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